

**The prominent architect Alexander Iosifovich Bernardazzi
(1831–1907)
(on the occasion of his 190th anniversary)**

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This year marks the 190th birthday of the famous Swiss architect of Italian origin A.I. Bernardazzi, who is also known for creating various historic buildings in Ukraine, Bessarabia and Poland. Archival documents served as evidence of the beginning of Bernardazzi's architectural career, when the Bessarabian Road and Construction Commission appointed him as technician for the urban planning of the towns Akkerman and Bendery in 1853 and also for building some bridges and causeways in those districts. He took part in the organization of the third market in the Forest square in Kishinev in September of 1855. This was the first mission of his creativity in Kishinev. According to the Service lists Alexander Bernardazzi executed his duty as municipal architect from 1856 to 1878 and replaced another architect Luca Zaushkevich. All his following monumental buildings became the best examples of European architecture by their style, form and quality. He participated in the design and construction of many buildings as the temporal theatre, Lutheran school, railway station, Greek Church, Manuk-bey's palace, etc. in Bessarabia. As for Kishinev, the architect Bernardazzi has done the beautification of paving many streets, the construction of urban water supply and the cast-iron rail in the city park. Also, he attended many architect's meetings, where interesting reports referring to the theater, some windows, fire safety of buildings, and so on were read. After the arrival in Odessa in 1878, Alexander Bernardazzi continued to participate in designing social and civil building in Bessarabia. For his enormous creative contribution to urban development, he was appreciated by being nominated honorable citizen of Kishinev and member of the Bessarabian department of the Imperial Russian technical society.